

IMAGE COMPRESSION USING NONUNIFORM SAMPLES WITH CONTROLLED COMPRESSION RATIOS

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ABSTRACT

The image compression process is an effective approach to ease the bulk storage requirement of digital images. In this study the compression using spline functions to obtain nonuniform spaced data samples from the image contours was examined. It is possible to control the compression ratio under the least square criterion. The image surface was also reconstructed from the samples using triangle element method. The nonuniform sample selection results were evaluated in terms of object feature extraction and information preservation.

INTRODUCTION

A two dimensional digital image is usually represented as a two dimensional matrix of gray levels. The value of a matrix element, $f(i, j)$ corresponds to the gray level of a pixel located at i -th row and j -th column. Although this kind of image representation allows convenient ways to display images as two dimensional intensity patterns, it often requires a very large amount of storage space in computer. One approach to solve this storage problem is to represent an image as a set of contours.^{1,2} A digital image can be viewed as a two-dimensional intensity function, and the function can be visualized as a surface with the height equal to the gray levels. The image, then, can be reduced to a record of contours with the gray level of each contour specified. Another approach is to represent the image as a set of gray level points non-uniformly sampled from the image plane.^{3,4,5} It is commonly known that the object of interests in an image is localized in many cases, and the major portion of the image does not vary much in gray levels. Uniform spatial sampling seems to be wasteful in areas where not much gray level variations exist. Hence, nonuniform spatial sampling is expected to reduce the total amount of data of the image as well as to extract the information of interest. This characteristic of the nonuniform sampling is advantageous in pattern matching

or recognition. It is interesting to see how information of the image signal is condensed compared to the original image.

In this study the above two approaches, the contour representation and the nonuniform spatial sampling, were combined to obtain an approximation of the image signal for the purpose of data compression and information extraction. The compression ratio in the reduction of the image signal was controlled to determine how the image signal would be approximated along with the decrease of the number of data points. The experiments in this study can be divided into three phases, I) contour extraction, II) nonuniform sample selection, and III) surface reconstruction.

CONTOUR EXTRACTION

Due to possible existence of noise in the original image, a 3×3 average filtering was operated on the original image before the contour extraction. The contour extraction here utilizes a tracing type of algorithm where the number of layers out of the image surface can be specified by the user and the layers are evenly distributed from the maximum gray level to the minimum gray level. Three forms of outputs are generated from the contouring process.

1. The layer record: this record contains the gray scale of each layer and the number of contours on each layer.

2. The contour record: each contour is coded as a sequence of pairs (x, y) representing the coordinates of connected points along the contour. The sequences are concatenated together with two labels at the beginning of each sequence. These labels show the number of points in each contour and the contour type (open or closed).

3. The character map: this is a character matrix with the same dimensions as the original image. An alphabet from A to Z is used to represent the projection of all contours onto the image plane. This output will be used in the nonuniform sample selection process.

Also, a threshold value is specified in this algorithm to eliminate contours with less number of points than the value. This thresholding is expected to have a smoothing effect for noisy images.

NONUNIFORM SAMPLE SELECTION

Since the contour of a natural image can have any arbitrary shape, the coordinates of data points representing the contour, (x_i, y_i) where $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$, are considered as a function of arc length z_i . z_i are the independent variable such that $z_i < z_{i+1}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$. For the interval $[a, b]$ with $a < z_1 < b$, the purpose is to select N uneven knots to approximate the contour. N is derived from a certain compression ratio and the number of data points on the contour. The total number of data points to be selected from all contours (NTOTAL) is given by multiplying the total number of initial data points with a desired compression ratio. Then, N points out of NTOTAL are allocated to each contour according to the ratio between the number of data points on the contour and the total points of all contours. Two cubic spline functions (piecewise polynomial with $k = 3$), S_x and S_y of these N knots are expressed as

$$S_x(z) = \sum_{i=-k}^N C_{x_i} M_{i,k+1}(z)$$

$$S_y(z) = \sum_{i=-k}^N C_{y_i} M_{i,k+1}(z)$$

S_x and S_y are the weighted sum of normalized B-splines $M_{i,k+1}(z)$ of k -th order and C_{x_i} and C_{y_i} are the weighting coefficients. Our objective now can be rephrased as selecting N knots to have the spline functions, $S_x(z)$ and $S_y(z)$ which fit the contour data points close enough as specified. To measure the closeness of fit, the weighted sum of squared residuals is defined as

$$\delta = \sum_{j=0}^m w_j [(x_j - S_x(z_j))^2 + (y_j - S_y(z_j))^2]$$

Where w_j is a positive weight which controls how closely S_x and S_y should fit the individual data point. In our case w_j is a function of contour density which is given by

$$w_j = w_0 + NC\Delta w$$

where w_0 : reference weight
 NC : maximum number of contours within the current neighborhood
 Δw : incremental weight

Hence, the coefficients C_x and C_y in the above spline functions are determined by the least square approximation to the original contour, but the smoothness of the spline functions is not considered here. In other words, a set of N knots which minimizes δ is chosen to approximate the contour.

The uneven knot selection algorithm in this study follows the method by Dierckx⁶ which chooses a set of knots according to the closeness norm, δ , subjected to the constraint, $\delta \leq S$ (S is given, non-negative constant), and also the smoothness norm is such that the discontinuities in the k -th derivative of the spline function are as small as possible. Dierckx's method is modified here to obtain a fixed number of uneven spaced data points from the contours, leaving the smoothness factor out of consideration and minimizing the closeness measure. The approximated contours were recorded in the output in the same format as the contour record used in the contour extraction phase.

SURFACE RECONSTRUCTION

To reconstruct an image surface we have to find a smooth function, $F(x_k, y_k)$, for a set of uneven spaced data points, (x_k, y_k, f_k) , $k = 1, 2 \dots$ NTOTAL, obtained in the previous phase. The triangle element method was chosen in this study as a local interpolation method which keeps the reconstruction processing time reasonable, and the algorithm reported by Lawson⁷ was adopted here.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND EVALUATION

Two different images, one with big objects of interests (runways) and the other with many small objects (houses), were tested with five different compression ratios in the experiment. Both the original and the reconstructed images were represented as a 256 by 256 matrix of 256 gray levels. Several input parameters are involved in the compression experiment discussed above, but they were fixed to certain values except the compression ratio. In the phase I the number of layers form the image surface was set to ten. The threshold value for the contour size in this phase was fixed to five, and the contours of less than five points were eliminated. The positive weight, w_j in the phase III was obtained from w_0 and Δw , which were fixed respectively to 0.8 and 0.2.

The compression effects with ratios of five, ten, twenty, thirty and forty were evaluated by examining the results from the nonuniform sampling phase and the reconstruction phases. Since the compression ratio is controlled in the nonuniform sampling phase, the effect of the compression ratio on contour shapes was examined in the comparison of the original contours extracted in the phase I to the approximated contours yielded in the phase II. As expected, the uneven spaced

Fig. 1 The original of the runway image

Fig. 2 The original of the housing area image

Fig. 3 The reconstructed image of Fig. 1
Compression ratio = 5

Fig. 4 The reconstructed image of Fig. 2
Compression ratio = 5

Fig. 5 The reconstructed image of Fig. 1
Compression ratio = 20

Fig. 6 The reconstructed image of Fig. 2
Compression ratio = 20

Fig. 7 The reconstructed image of Fig. 1
Compression ratio = 30

sample representation loses more details as the compression ratio increases. The big objects retain their fundamental shapes even with high compression ratios, whereas the small objects lose their features or disappear when the compression ratio is high. The reconstructed images yielded in the phase III are shown in Fig. 3 through 7 with the original images in Fig. 1 and 2. As Fig. 2 shows, severe distortion was introduced to the housing image even in the case of small compression ratios, and small objects such as houses and narrow streets lost their fundamental shapes. On the other hand, the runways' shapes and features were preserved in the reconstructed images from the data points sampled even with such a high compression ratio as thirty. However, the higher compression ratios deteriorated the clearness of the edges of the big objects.

These experimental results suggest that the image compression with high compression ratios is not desirable in terms of preserving the whole original image, especially in the case that the original image has many small objects. However, if we are interested in processing comparatively big objects in the input image, the small details of the objects can be smoothed out in the process of compression, and the main feature of the objects can be kept. This characteristic may be advantageous in such cases as the pattern recognition or image matching processes where the fundamental shapes of the objects are often more important than small details.

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